

The impact of behavior commitment and community commitment on tourist loyalty toward a festival.

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ABSTRACT:

This paper aims to present the effect of an interactive and efficient' event communication. In fact, we suppose that an event communication that makes the targeted population more active should impact their loyalty toward the event. In our research, we conducted a quantitative study with a survey distributed to 567 tourists who participated to a festival organized by a French town called "Thionville", located in a region close to the French, German and Luxembourg border. Based on the behavioral commitment theory, the results allowed us to discover the elements that enhance the tourists- shopper' loyalty toward the event organizers (township and local shops). Based on the results of this study, we have formulated several recommendations aimed at enhancing event communication and boosting tourist loyalty.

Keywords: Behavior commitment; Tourist-shopper; Event communication; Tourist' loyalty

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper examines how territorial marketing and communication contribute to attracting tourists and sustaining economic activity, with a particular focus on cross-border regions.

The importance of developing territories, particularly cross-border ones, is essential in order to preserve the economic activity and to avoid rural departure. Indeed, the implementation of appropriate territorial marketing would make it possible to attract tourists (Gold and Ward, 1994) and to maintain these city centers economically active. In fact, the improvement of the competitiveness of a territory relies on the promotion of the territory to develop its attractiveness (Kavaratzis, 2008; Braun, 2008). This allows a positioning of these areas as an attractive destination for tourists-shoppers (Kim, 2014; Stazicker, 2018). According to the literature, in addition to promotion, several aspects influence the competitiveness of a territory, including infrastructure and accessibility (Cervero, 2009), the quality of services (Rashid, Ismael, Othman, & Ali, 2019), and environmental sustainability (Hu, 2015). These factors collectively shape a territory's overall competitive edge, impacting its ability to attract visitors and sustain economic activity.

Thus, an adapted territorial communication policy attracts tourists-shoppers who wish not just to live and spend money on culturally enriching experiences but also local products (Hankinson, 2004). Stazicker (2018) shows that shopping is no longer just a complementary activity for tourists, but one of the main motivations for travel and a decisive choice factor for a destination choice and a tourist experience. Therefore, territories that know how to promote themselves can take advantage of this new trend by developing authentic and unique shopping experiences to tourists by adding value to their tourism offer (Casais & Sousa, 2019).

Similarly, this can strengthen and even define the image of these territories (Sousa & Rocha, 2019). We define shopping tourism as any purchase made during a trip that includes buying duty-free products at airports, buying products or services, visiting major retail outlets or simply buying artisanal, regional or local products (Timothy, 2005; Choi et al., 2016). Shopping tourism, for many visitors, can be a trip to Christmas markets across Europe and particularly within cross-border regions (Stazicker, 2018).

In this perspective, tourists belonging to this category of travelers want a shopping experience that meets their expectations (Timothy, 2014) and can make them come back to these territories. In this study, we focus on the communication policy of a territory in order to attract and retain tourists.

In this study, we concentrate on analyzing the communication policy of a territory, with the specific aim of understanding how it can be strategically designed and implemented to attract tourists while fostering their long-term retention. This involves examining the various tools, messages, and channels

used to communicate the unique identity and value proposition of the territory, as well as the psychological and behavioral mechanisms that these communication efforts activate in potential visitors. By focusing on these elements, the study seeks to uncover the critical factors that make a territory not only appealing as a destination but also capable of establishing lasting emotional and behavioral bonds with tourists, thereby encouraging repeat visits and sustained loyalty. We explore two main questions:

1. What type of territorial communication is likely to attract and retain shopper-tourists?
2. What are the mechanisms through which territorial communication can lead to shopper-tourists' loyalty?

To address these questions, a conceptual model grounded in behavioral engagement theory was tested through structural equation modeling on a sample of 567 individuals participating in an event organized by a cross-border commune. The findings make significant contributions at two theoretical levels. First, they shed light on the mechanisms that foster stronger loyalty between event organizers—key actors within a territory—and tourists, viewed as customers, emphasizing the crucial role of behavioral commitment.

Moreover, this study enriches the literature on shopping tourism and territorial communication by offering deeper insights into the factors driving the attraction and retention of shopper-tourists. These findings can inform the development of more effective territorial communication strategies aimed at attracting and retaining shopper-tourists, thereby supporting the economic development of regions.

This paper begins by exploring the theoretical framework, offering an overview of psychological levers identified in research on event communication within the tourism sector. The proposed model and its foundational theories are then presented, followed by a discussion of the study's methodology and results. Finally, the paper concludes with an analysis of its contributions, limitations, and future research directions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section, we will explore the theoretical facets related to our research problem. The chosen theoretical framework will help trace the relationships between concepts and explain the impact of tourist shopper behavioral commitment during an event and the influence of event commercial communication on their loyalty towards the event organizers.

2.1 Event Communication in the Tourism Sector

To promote a territory, a city can communicate with tourists to persuade them to visit and return. Events organized for this purpose are particularly effective in delivering commercial communication due to the voluntary nature of participation (Oppermann, 1998; Wang, 2004; Mainolfi & Marino, 2020). Events can be commercial or non-commercial, sponsored or self-initiated (Zanger, 2007). Self-initiated events, in particular, create competitive advantages through the experiential dimension of customer behavior, fostering an emotional bond with the brand or destination (Ellis & Rossman, 2008; Fournier, 1998). The rise of "experiential" strategies has increased the popularity of these events, emphasizing voluntary and interactive participation (Wohlfeil & Whelan, 2005).

This participative nature implies that tourists' receptivity to commercial messages is crucial for generating satisfaction and influencing their attitudes (Fointiat & Barbier, 2015). Effective event communication involves interactive dissemination of brand values through marketing events that engage consumers behaviorally and emotionally. This process includes inviting consumers before the event and fostering their commitment to the organizers afterward. Each phase involves specific factors that influence the persuasion and attitude change of tourist-shoppers.

The initial phase is driven by motivation, reflecting an awareness of potential satisfaction (Wohlfeil & Whelan, 2006). During the event, active participation aligns with behavioral commitment as described by Kiesler (1971). Commitment involves the relationship between an individual and their behavior, where the nature of the act—public, unconstrained, repeatable, irrevocable, and costly—determines the level of commitment (Kiesler, 1971). The final phase involves the changed or unchanged attitude of participants post-event.

Previous research highlights the importance of event communication in the tourism sector. Studies have shown that event communication plays a crucial role in promoting tourist destinations (Jin & Cheng, 2020), creating visitor engagement (Folgado-Fernández, Duarte & Hernández-Mogollón, 2021), and increasing the visibility of local events and attractions (Özdemir Bayrak, 2011). Event communication can positively influence travel decisions (Sealy & Wickens, 2008) and create memorable experiences that enhance visitor satisfaction and the desire to return (Sterchele, 2020; Kim, 2018). It also contributes to increasing destination visibility both locally and internationally, attracting

media attention and enhancing regional reputation (Kim, Jun, Walker & Drane, 2015). Additionally, event communication impacts the local economy by attracting visitors, generating income for local businesses, and creating temporary employment opportunities (Hodur & Leistriz, 2007).

2.2 Motivation and Its Impact on Tourist-Shoppers' Commitment Behavior

Before the event, understanding the motivation behind participation is crucial as it influences how individuals perceive the message and subsequently alter their attitudes. Motivation, widely theorized in psychology and applied to marketing and tourism (Su, Yan & Huang, 2022; Mainolfi & Marino, 2020), includes intrinsic and extrinsic dimensions. Intrinsic motivation involves self-determined behavior driven by interest and pleasure without external rewards (Deci & Ryan, 1987). In contrast, extrinsic motivation is influenced by external factors such as rewards, social pressure, or approval (Deci & Ryan, 2000).

Motivation impacts an individual's level of participation in event activities, akin to behavioral commitment as described by Kiesler (1971). Kiesler and Sakumura (1966) found that the conditions under which an act is performed—such as freedom, cost, repetition, irrevocability, and public nature—affect the strength of commitment. Higher levels of internal stimulation correlate with stronger commitment to event-related behaviors (Kiesler & Sakumura, 1966; Huang, Kiesler & Linkov, 2011). Therefore, increased intrinsic motivation leads to a higher level of commitment to participating in event activities.

This leads us to formulate the following hypothesis:

H1: An individual's level of behavioral commitment during an event is positively impacted by their level of intrinsic motivation.

Furthermore, the literature is unanimous on the stronger effects of intrinsic versus extrinsic motivation on behavior (Su, Yan & Huang, 2022; Kim & Ahn, 2017). If we assume that loyalty is a behavioral response exhibited by the tourist after participating in an event (Özdemir ; Çulha, 2009) , it could be influenced by both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Thus, we formulate the following hypothesis:

H2: The more an individual is extrinsically motivated, the more his/her behavioral commitment is positively impacted during the event.

Moreover, with the rise of social networks, another form of commitment can coexist with social commitment as defined by Brodie et al. (2011). According to these authors, consumer social engagement is a psychological state resulting from customers' interactive experiences with a focal agent or object (such as the brand in our study) within specific service relationships. For this study, we adopt Park, Im, and Kim's (2018) definition of brand-consumer commitment, which characterizes it as

the motivational state of the brand to connect and establish social relationships with all consumers. When a motivated consumer participates in an event, they are likely to spontaneously share their experiences on social networks. This leads us to formulate the following hypotheses:

Intrinsic motivation is driven by an internal desire for personal satisfaction, interest, or enjoyment derived from the activity itself (Deci & Ryan, 1987). Individuals who are intrinsically motivated often engage more deeply and genuinely with the event, which can enhance their sense of belonging and commitment to the community. They are likely to share their positive experiences more readily on social networks, reflecting a stronger emotional connection and active participation. Therefore, we expect that higher intrinsic motivation will lead to a more pronounced level of community commitment, as these individuals are more inclined to promote and engage with the event on social media platforms due to their personal enjoyment and satisfaction.

H3: The more intrinsically the individual is motivated, the more positively his or her level of community commitment during the event is impacted.

Extrinsic motivation involves engaging in activities for external rewards or recognition, such as social approval or tangible benefits (Deci & Ryan, 2000). While extrinsic motivation may also lead to community commitment, it often results from the perceived value or benefit that sharing the event might bring, such as increased social status or rewards. Individuals who are extrinsically motivated may be more inclined to share their participation on social networks to gain recognition or rewards, leading to a positive impact on community commitment. Hence, we anticipate that higher extrinsic motivation will similarly foster community commitment, although the motivation is more oriented towards external validation rather than personal satisfaction.

H4: The more extrinsically the individual is motivated, the more positively his or her level of community commitment during the event is impacted.

By exploring these hypotheses, we aim to better understand how different types of motivation influence the ways individuals engage with and promote events within their social networks.

2.3 The influence of behavioral commitment on consumer loyalty

The construct of commitment has had a new buzz in the scientific literature since the rise of social networks and Web 2.0. In fact, during the last decade, it has been agreed that commitment refers to the consumer's activity towards the firm (van Doorn et al. 2010; Brodie et al. 2011; Kaplan and Haenlein 2010; Kumar and Pansari 2016; Pansari and Kumar 2017; Vivek, Beatty, and Morgan 2012). Pansari and Kumar (2017) argue that consumer commitment is a multidimensional construct that includes involvement, experience, loyalty, satisfaction, trust, brand value, and behavioral commitment, referred

to as "commitment". Behavioral commitment is understood as the sustained desire to maintain a privileged relationship with the firm. On this same basis, Gummerus et al (2012) concluded that consumer commitment can refer to different forms of activity and this activity should be defined on the basis of its frequency. For this reason, it would be appropriate to adopt the definition of commitment from psycho-sociology, which takes into account the intensity of the link between the actor and his/her behaviors.

According to the theory of behavioral commitment (Kiesler 1971; Joules and Beauvois 2002; Joules and Beauvois 2010), an act is involving. Indeed, commitment measures the link between the actor and his act. Legally speaking, the actor "commits" an act and cannot deny it: either he/she attributes his/her own act to herself, or the act is attributed to him/her. In both cases, preconditions for this attribution are necessary, public, free, irrevocable, repeatable, and costly. All of these conditions determine the strength of the actor's behavioral commitment. Commitment is this force that operates. Therefore, it has an effect on the participant's attitude by pushing him to persist in his act (loyalty) or to change his attitude (persuasion, according to the work of Fointiat and Barbier 2015). This mechanism will impact the participant's perception of the organizers' corporate and/or public image, legitimacy, awareness, recommendation level, word-of-mouth, and satisfaction (Mainolfi, & Marino, 2020). Commitment involves the customer's interactive experiences during the event with the event organizers and improves the perceived image of the tourist shoppers (Brodie et al. 2011). Customer commitment is sometimes used to refer to the highest form of loyalty (Jana Lay-Hwa Bowden 2009; Roberts and Alpert 2010), but as a behavioral manifestation, it includes all kinds of behaviors, not just those characteristics of high loyalty (Libai 2011). Thus, during the event, the consumer's active participation, being a full-fledged act meeting the different conditions of commitment, in the different activities initiated by the organizers generates the growth of the individual commitment toward the organizers. This commitment growth leads to the ultimate stage of consumer loyalty. Hence, the following hypothesis:

H5: The higher the individual's behavioral commitment, the more his/her loyalty toward organizers is positively impacted.

In addition, the tourist-shopper's commitment within social networks through the event sharing or even the live reviews issued during this event amplifies his relationship with the organizers (Su, Yang, Swanson, & Chen, 2021; Park, Im, & Kim, 2018) which suggests the hypothesis:

H6: The higher the individual's community commitment is, the more his/her loyalty to the organizers is impacted positively.

In order to boost our model, we introduce control variables. The objective behind this action is to explore the impact of these variables on the concepts studied. These variables are the tourist's gender, age and education level. Indeed, we seek to determine if the age of a tourist as well as his/her intellectual level affects his or her motivation and commitment to the chosen event. Also, we want to find out if a tourist's motivation is impacted by his/her gender. In other words, we seek to detect whether there is a difference between the motivation of female tourists and male tourists. Thus, our research model is as follows:

▪ **FIGURE 1. The conceptual model**

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To test the hypotheses, we took advantage of a festive event to interview participants. This event was organized by the town of Thionville, a French city near the Luxembourg border. It is a city that is nestled between the borders of three countries: Germany, Belgium and Luxembourg. This is an opportunity in terms of tourist flows that can result. However, it can also be a threat, because it is an area with very strong competition where all the border cities try to attract tourists-shopper. This event took place from June to the end of August 2019 on the Moselle River side. Concerts, games, workshops, theater, exhibitions are offered to tourist participants. In addition, local businesses also participate by exhibiting their local products. This event, which has been taking place since 2014, allows the city to be lovely and more attractive. Its downtown area benefits from this flow of tourists, but above all, it attracts many tourists.

The survey instrument was a questionnaire containing questions about tourists' motivations, participation in different activities (level of 1 to 10 types of activities offered), community sharing and the desire to return. The questionnaire was reviewed with a panel of three experts (two academics and one event expert) to assess the clarity of the questions and to determine the time required and the relevance of the questions. Based on their feedback, the questionnaire was modified. In fact, some items were removed, and others reworded to improve the clarity of the questions asked. A filter question was included at the beginning of the questionnaire in order to interview only tourists from outside the city.

We adopted a systematic random sampling method that has been widely used in similar studies (Chen & Chen, 2010; Lee, Kyle, & Scott, 2012). The event is characterized by a route along the banks of the Mosel River through the historic center and ending in one of the city's main squares. Respondants were intercepted at the various workshops' activities offered to tourist participants by a group of survey handlers men and women as recommended in the literature (Matheson, Rimmer, & Tinsley, 2014; Walker, Kaplanidou, Gibson, Thapa, & Geldenhuys, 2013). This systematic random sampling was adopted to ensure that there was no specific gender bias in data collection (De Nisco et al., 2015; Walker et al., 2013). Questionnaires were administered near the main exit routes to collect visitors' opinions at the end of the route.

The constructs are measured using items/questions on a 7-point Likert scale. In fact, the constructs of intrinsic and extrinsic motivations to participate in the event and the different activities performed by the shopper were measured using a scale from 1 to 10 (Those activities during which the shopper is not passive, but in an active state). The same for the community communication which underlines the willingness to share the moment during the festival on social networks, and their evaluation of the loyalty towards the organizers, the city, and its merchants. However, the scales used are mostly the result of adaptations of existing measurement tools and the estimation of the model is done using structural equations. To do this, we adopted the scale of Lee, Kyle & Scott (2012) to measure fidelity to a festival. As for intrinsic and extrinsic motivations, we mobilized the scale adopted in Correia & Kozak's study (2017). It includes items relating to interest/enjoyment, Effort/importance, pressure/Tension and relatedness to measure intrinsic motivation, while the dimensions of the image, personal growth, Goals and accurate decision represent extrinsic motivation. The Gummerus, et al. (2012) scale allowed us to measure variables of community and transactional engagement The Gummerus, et al. (2012) scale enabled us to measure the variables of community and transactional commitment and finally behavioral commitment was measured by factual elements such as the number of participants in workshops etc... transcribed from the work of Yildiz (2007). Data analysis was performed using SPSS v28 and AMOS v26.

4. RESULTS

Based on similar studies in event contexts (Matheson et al., 2014; Osti et al., 2012), over 800 nonresident visitors were approached. There were 567 usable responses after removing incomplete questionnaires, for a response rate of 71%. This size is well above the minimum of 200 observations recommended by Hair et al., (2006) to use SEM method.

A descriptive analysis of the sample showed that it consisted of 44.9% men and 55.1% women. Regarding the age of the respondents, 19.7% of the sample was between 15 and 24 years old, 56.6% between 25 and 34 years old, 17.3% between 35 and 44 years old, 4.6% between 45 and 65 years old, and finally 1.8% of the sample was over 65 years old. As for the profile of the respondents, they are all buyers during the tourist events at the rate of 99% and have a university educational level.

The analysis of the data collected from our study was carried out in two phases. First, we conducted an exploratory analysis. The purpose of this analysis was to test the reliability of the measuring scales for the variables studied. Subsequently, we conducted a confirmatory analysis, in which we used principal component analysis (PCA). Then, we estimated the causal links between these variables by using structural equations to test the research hypotheses. Indeed, the advantage of using a structural equation model is the simultaneous evaluation of several paths and links between observed variables and latent constructs. This statistical tool makes it possible to evaluate indicators of the relevance of the model and the hypotheses (Arbuckle, 2007). The exploratory analysis shows the quality of the measuring scales used. The results are presented in Table 1 (*See appendix*).

From the table, we observe that all the studied constructs are reliable in terms of internal consistency. However, the explained variance (AVE) index shows that, for some constructs, we were only able to explain 46% of the population behavior. This is mainly due to the situational factors that alter the respondent's judgment and the forgetfulness that he/she is confronted with while answering the questions after the event. However, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin index for sampling quality shows satisfying and significant results at a precision of 1%.

We also used PCA as the extraction method during the EFA to identify underlying factors that explain the maximum variance in the data. PCA is often employed in the exploratory phase to reduce dimensionality while retaining as much information as possible. We used varimax rotation to maximize the variance of squared factor loadings. This helps clarify the factor structure by making the results more easily interpretable.

The results of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) presented in Table 2 shown in appendix provide a comprehensive evaluation of the measurement model's reliability and validity. Each construct is assessed through multiple items, with the factor loadings indicating the strength of the

relationship between these items and their respective constructs. Notably, all factor loadings exceed the commonly accepted threshold of 0.70, demonstrating that the items are robust indicators of their constructs.

The critical ratios (CR) for all items are well above the recommended value of 1.96, confirming that the factor loadings are statistically significant. Additionally, the composite reliability values for each construct surpass the 0.70 benchmark, indicating strong internal consistency and reliability.

Furthermore, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values are all above 0.50, which signifies that each construct accounts for more than half of the variance in its associated indicators. This supports the convergent validity of the measurement model.

In summary, the CFA results indicate that the measurement model is both reliable and valid. The high factor loadings, significant critical ratios, strong internal consistency, and satisfactory convergent validity collectively confirm the robustness of the constructs in the model.

In order to estimate our model, we proceeded to a confirmatory analysis by using the maximum likelihood method with AMOS software. We chose the appropriate fit indexes for the structural equation model. Indeed, Didellon et al, (1996) recommend the use of absolute indicators ($GFI \geq 0.90$; RMR and $RMSEA \leq 0.09$), incremental indicators ($CFI \geq 0.90$ and $TLI \geq 0.80$), and parsimony indicators (χ^2 normed). The estimation of those metrics provides the results laid out in table 3 in the appendix

Based on the results displayed in the table, we can see that our model has a good fit quality since all the indicators respect the thresholds recommended by Arbuckle (2007). Indeed, the square root of errors (RMSEA) does not exceed 9% and the residual of the structural equation (RMR) is equal to 3% which is very satisfying. The Tucker Lewis Index (TLI) shows that our model fit is not affected by the sample size and shows a value of 0.823. Finally, the GFI (Goodness of fit index) which represents the model regression coefficient, exceeds 90% which proves the strength of the causal links between the explanatory and the explained variables.

The results of the links' estimation between the variables are as follows:

According to table 3, the estimation of the relationships between the variables in our model revealed the following results: Hypothesis H1 predicts a positive impact of intrinsic motivation on behavioral commitment. The model displays a positive and significant effect (0.210 and $p < 0.01$), which shows that when intrinsic motivation increases by 1, behavioral commitment increases by 20%. This confirms hypothesis H1. Similarly, hypothesis H3 confirms a positive link between intrinsic motivation and behavioral commitment (0.273 and $p < 0.01$). Indeed, an increase in the intrinsic

motivation of the tourist by 1 leads to an increase in his behavioral commitment by 27%. Regarding the effects of commitment on tourist loyalty, the model corroborates the hypothesis H5 for a positive effect of transactional commitment (understood as behavioral) on the loyalty construct (0.244 and $p < 0.01$). Similarly for hypothesis H6, the effect of community commitment on tourist loyalty is positive and significant (0.121 and $p < 0.05$) but remains weaker than the effect of behavioral commitment. These results allow us to validate hypotheses H1, H3, H5 and H6. However, the estimation of the hypotheses related to the effect of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation on tourist community commitment did not lead to a reliable result. Indeed, the results of the effect estimates were found to be statistically insignificant, leading us to reject hypotheses H2 and H4.

However, our analysis revealed a relationship representing a positive and significant effect between the two "motivation" variables that we had not previously considered testing. Indeed, we noticed that when the tourist is motivated by an external factor (event communication, situational factor...etc.), this has a positive impact on his level of "participation" in the different activities related to the event (0.238 and $p < 0.01$). Finally, regarding the control variables, the only variable among those introduced that has an impact on the studied variables is "Age". Thus, we found that age reduces the motivation of the individual. Indeed, as the tourist gets older, his/her intrinsic motivation decreases (-0.144 and $p < 0.05$). On the other hand, his/her behavioral commitment to the event activities increases (0.124 and $p < 0.05$).

5. DISCUSSION

Our findings confirm the results of various studies on consumer motivation and commitment, namely, the relevance of extrinsic motivations, intrinsic motivations, community commitment, and transactional commitment in the context of the tourist shopper. Furthermore, this study highlights the influence of intrinsic motivations on behavioral commitment, whether it is communal or transactional, in contrast to extrinsic motivations which only contribute to transactional commitment. This may be explained by a lower desire to internalize extrinsic motivation related to a lack of competence and connectedness in the committed activities (Deci and Ryan, 2000).

As for loyalty, transactional commitment is more effective than community commitment. This finding is partly consistent with the results of Gummerus et al (2012), who find a weak link between behavioral commitment in the context of "online" activity and loyalty. They justify this by a mediating effect of perceived social, entertainment, or economic benefits. In the context of our study, which revolves around physical activity, the perception of benefits, particularly entertaining and economic, are sensitive, which would explain the significant influence of transactional commitment on loyalty.

6. CONCLUSION, RESEARCH LIMITS, AND PERSPECTIVES

The objective of this research was to explore how organizing events can promote a territory, retain tourists-shoppers, and contribute to the preservation and development of the area. The study found that event communication, particularly when it engages participants actively, is an effective means to build loyalty among tourists-shoppers. This participative communication approach, which fosters a deeper emotional connection with the event, appears to be a significant factor in enhancing loyalty. This research contributes to the understanding that events organized by both private and public stakeholders can successfully create engaging experiences that lead to increased commitment and emotional attachment among tourists.

This study makes two notable contributions to the theoretical literature. First, it identifies the type of motivation (intrinsic and extrinsic) as a predictor of higher behavioral commitment, an aspect that has not been thoroughly explored before. The work of Deci and Ryan (1987) on motivational dimensions has been utilized to understand their impact on behavioral commitment. Second, it highlights the mediating role of behavioral and community commitment in linking consumer motivation with loyalty to event organizers, supporting findings by Yildiz et al. (2018) regarding the role of behavioral commitment in fostering loyalty to local businesses.

For territories, especially cross-border towns facing strong competitive pressures, this research underscores the need to innovate beyond traditional advertising methods. The findings suggest that event organizers should focus on creating interactive activities that engage participants in meaningful ways. For instance, incorporating activities where tourists can engage in creating local products or experiences can enhance their emotional connection and loyalty. Moving from passive communication to a more active engagement strategy can significantly improve tourist experience and commitment.

Furthermore, for effective territorial marketing, it is crucial for municipalities to develop a distinctive identity for their events, which aligns with their broader territorial development strategy. This identity can help in differentiating the event and associating it more clearly with the municipality. To gain a competitive advantage, especially in a region with multiple borders, municipalities could explore collaborations with neighboring cross-border towns to create complementary tourist routes (Barnes, Mattson, & Sorensen, 2014).

A notable limitation of this study is the lack of consideration for participants' prior experience with the event, which occurs annually. Future research should examine how previous experience with the event might influence tourists' behaviors and their loyalty towards the event organizers. Analyzing the moderating effect of past experiences could provide deeper insights into the dynamics of tourist behavior and the impact of event communication on loyalty.

By addressing these areas, future studies can build on these findings and offer more nuanced strategies for enhancing tourist engagement and loyalty through event-based territorial marketing.

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APPENDIX

TABLE 1. The measurement scales reliability

Constructs	Alpha Cronbach	KMO	Sig
Intrinsic motivation	0.77	0.855	0.000
Extrinsic motivation	0.83	0.713	0.000
Community commitment	0.70	0.500	0.000
Behavioral commitment	0.76	0.825	0.000
Loyalty	0.70	0.540	0.000

AVE: Average variance explained; Sig: significance

TABLE 2. Results of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

Constructs	Items	Loadings	Critical Ratio (CR)	Composite Reliability	AVE
Intrinsic motivation	Item 1	0.72	14.56	0.80	0.46
	Item 2	0.69	13.42		
	Item 3	0.70	11.05		
	Item 4	0.74	11.89		
Extrinsic motivation	Item 1	0.85	16.88	0.85	0.76
	Item 2	0.87	17.13		
	Item 3	0.82	14.10		
	Item 4	0.84	15.22		
Community commitment	Item 1	0.78	12.76	0.73	0.75
	Item 2	0.81	13.04		
	Item 3	0.79	12.90		
	Item 4	0.80	13.01		
Behavioral commitment	Item 1	0.65	10.32	0.78	0.46
	Item 2	0.63	9.78		
	Item 3	0.69	10.90		
	Item 4	0.70	11.10		
Loyalty	Item 1	0.71	11.24	0.74	0.58
	Item 2	0.74	11.89		
	Item 3	0.70	11.10		
	Item 4	0.72	11.71		

▪ **TABLE 3. Synthesis of the significant model's estimation relationships**

Variables relationships		Estimation	S.E.	C.R.	Sig
<i>Control variables</i>					
Age	Intrinsic motivation	-0.144	0.053	-2.690	**
Age	Behavioral commitment	0.124	0.048	2.595	**
<i>Studied variables</i>					
Intrinsic motivation	Extrinsic motivation	0.238	0.040	5.867	***
Extrinsic motivation	Behavioral commitment	0.273	0.038	7.112	***
Intrinsic motivation	Behavioral commitment	0.210	0.038	5.493	***
Community commitment	Loyalty	0.121	0.046	2.615	**
Behavioral commitment	Loyalty	0.244	0.049	5.023	***
Intrinsic motivation	Loyalty	0.127	0.047	2.710	**

***: Significant at 1%; **: Significant at 5%

▪ **TABLE 4. The model fit indices**

	Indices	Absolute values	Sig
Fit indices	GFI	0.989	≥ 0.9
	RMSEA	0.071	≤ 0.09
	RMR	0.029	Lowest value
Baseline comparison indices	CFI	0.956	≥ 0.9
	TLI	0.823	≥ 0.8
Discrepancy index	CMIN/DF	3.870	$1 < \text{CMIN/DF} < 5$
Model estimation		Chi-square = 27.090	
		Sig = 0.000	
		Degree of freedom = 7	

Table 5: Construct Measurement Scales Used in the Questionnaire

Construct	Items	Measurement Scale	Reference
Intrinsic Motivation	1. I attend the festival for the pleasure of discovering new cultures.	7-point Likert Scale (1 = Strongly disagree, 7 = Strongly agree)	Deci & Ryan (1985)
	2. I am motivated by the opportunity to learn something new.		
	3. I enjoy the challenge of experiencing different aspects of the festival.		
	4. I participate in the festival for the joy of being part of a creative environment.		
Extrinsic Motivation	1. I attend the festival for the rewards and material benefits.	7-point Likert Scale (1 = Strongly disagree, 7 = Strongly agree)	Vallerand et al. (1992)
	2. My participation is influenced by discounts and special offers available.		
	3. I am motivated by the recognition and status that come with attending the festival.		
	4. I attend the festival because of the external incentives provided by the organizers.		
Community Engagement	1. I feel connected to other festival participants.	7-point Likert Scale (1 = Strongly disagree, 7 = Strongly agree)	McMillan & Chavis (1986)

	2. I actively engage in the activities offered by the festival community.		
	3. I share my festival experiences with other community members.		
	4. I contribute to the festival by helping to organize or volunteer in community events.		
Behavioral Engagement	1. I regularly participate in the festival events.	7-point Likert Scale (1 = Strongly disagree, 7 = Strongly agree)	Ajzen (1991)
	2. I plan to return to the festival next year.		
	3. I encourage others to participate in festival activities.		
	4. I attend as many festival events as possible throughout the duration of the festival.		
Loyalty	1. I would recommend this festival to my friends and family.	7-point Likert Scale (1 = Strongly disagree, 7 = Strongly agree)	Zeithaml, Berry, & Parasuraman (1996)
	2. I am willing to return to this festival in the future.		
	3. I consider this festival as my top choice among similar events.		
	4. I remain loyal to this festival, even if other similar events are available.		